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Moral Education as Strategies for Improving Moral Behaviour of Children in Nigerian Baptist Convention Churches

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Abstract

The challenge of moral decadence in contemporary society has found its way into the Christian fold unnoticed through socialization, secularization, civilization, and modernization. The actualization of a well-balanced society, which used to be the Church's responsibility, now becomes vague and wanting. This paper discusses that moral education plays a vital role in shaping the character and behaviour of children, particularly within religious institutions such as Baptist Churches. As a tool for improving moral behaviour, Moral Education instils values and principles that guide individuals to make ethical decisions and conduct themselves virtuously. One of the goals of Baptist Churches in the Nigerian Baptist Convention is to impart moral values such as honesty, integrity, compassion, forgiveness, and love for others to all generations. Programs like the Sunday school, disciple's lifestyle, and others are a ready medium to accomplish this.

Keywords: Moral, Morality, Education, Children, Behaviour, Nigerian Baptist Convention Churches

Introduction

The concept of morals, morality, and moral education appeared in the world of scholarship more recently than ever as society and

stakeholders struggle to revive the decline and decadence in society's path. Christianity places a great emphasis on moral education as it believes that having a solid moral foundation is essential for living a life that follows the teachings of Jesus Christ. The writer of Deuteronomy in the Bible also charged everyone in the society to be responsible for the morals and character of children. The actualization of this is imperative for the introduction of moral education in contemporary society. For Christians, moral education is not just about following a set of rules but about developing an attitude and character that reflects Christ's virtues. This paper examines moral education compared to other forms of education employed to encourage high ethical standards among children. The possible challenges and obstacles in implementing moral education among children in Baptist churches will also be considered. Strategies for implementing intentional moral Education in Baptist churches will be suggested.

Concept of Morality and Moral Education

Morality is one of the essential things in life that speaks about how people behave in society, especially in this present generation. Williams (1973) described morality as the principle of doing things either wrongly or badly in life. It is the standards of behaviours and the principles of rights and wrongs. He further explained that morals are personal things to everyone. It differs from one person to another based on personal integrity and upbringing. Therefore, adhering to the moral standards of society becomes a duty for every member of society. Morality is an integral part of the educational process.

Christianity played a significant role in shaping moral values. The words of Jesus Christ and the principles found in the Bible have provided a solid ethical foundation for morality and human behaviour. One of the principles in Christianity is the awareness of one's creation in the image of God. That is, the peak of understanding of morality, because the God we serve is moral. He has given us an immortal soul to understand the orderliness of things established in his creation through the gifts of intelligence and reason. God has also given us free will to seek and love what is accurate, sound, and beautiful (Nauert 2017).

A glance at these two claims the Christians make about God that make morality so vitally important can further explain the Christian view of morals and morality in contemporary society: that Yahweh is a God who

acts in history and that Yahweh is moral; and that the God revealed in the Scripture is a God who acts. For the Christian, this seems self-evident, but it was not always so (Iheanacho 2010). Many people in the ancient world believed that God created the world and then set it on its course, much as a watchmaker builds a watch and then lets it run without interfering with its workings.

The essence of Christian morality is simply love. A reflection on the words of Jesus in Matthew chapter 22 laid a foundation for this principle; 'You must love the Lord your God with all your heart, soul, and mind. This is the greatest and the first commandment. The second resembles it: you must love your neighbour as yourself. Love, compassion, honesty, integrity, humility, and forgiveness are vital values Christians strive to uphold. Following Jesus's teachings and living according to Christian principles can lead a life of moral excellence and build a more just and compassionate society.

Moral Education is how children's relevant knowledge, attitudes, values, and skills are transmitted and developed. As such, it focuses on developing the cognitive, social, and emotional skills necessary for moral thinking, action, and feeling. It also concerns the practices and strategies that socializing agents use to equip children with the resources to address issues about right and wrong in their everyday lives. Kohlberg (2004) suggested that moral education is comparable to ethical thinking and decision-making in moral situations or dilemmas. He further stated that moral Education should help students develop the abilities and skills of critical thinking needed to make value-oriented ethical decisions in a contemporary society. Putri (2017) posited that moral Education is a form of teaching that helps develop children considered good, mannered, civic, honest, behaved, critical, healthy, compliant, traditional, and socially acceptable lifestyle. Many experts believe moral education is an umbrella term for emotional learning, social learning, effective cognitive development, moral reasoning, health education, life skills education, critical thinking, violence prevention, conflict resolution, ethical reasoning, and mediation. Moral Education has a lot to do with the life of children because, through it in various settings and institutions, children will be able to see why they need to behave well at home, in the community, in Church, and society. Moral education starts at home, where parents are responsible and morally upright.

Gunadi (2013) observed that the following are related to the concept of moral education:

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1. Character Education, which he described as education that has direct contact with the development of morals in children.
 2. Cognitive Morals as an educational approach based on the belief that children should learn democracy, justice, and other values when their morals are in the development process.
 3. Value clarification is the process of assisting children in being aware of and understanding what life is and clarifying what forms of behaviour are worth doing.

Moral education covers four pillars of teaching and learning: Character and Morality, the Individual and the Community, Civic Studies, and Cultural Studies (Althof 2006). All these four pillars complement one another. The cohesion and coherence of these four pillars will motivate a smooth moral development of children's behaviour because they will shape everything about them and affect them positively, even in the church setting. Moral education depends more on morality, values, and beliefs. It helps individuals lead the right path in life. It is more of an ethical education where you understand right and wrong, respect others, be humble, and pay gratitude. Children are not to be exempted from society's standard of morals in terms of what they do, eat, talk, and interact with adults and among their peer groups either in the Church or at home, and what they wear: all these affect others positively or negatively. Adeloje (2010) emphasized the need to address moral issues among children in the Baptist church early; this will help get it right at the beginning as they are on a journey. They will be able to meet the moral standards of society and represent the Baptist churches and denominations effectively. It will help them cope in the community and the society at large. Ola (2021) underscored that underpinning this suggestion is the implementation of a curriculum that includes the thinking, learning, and communication skills relevant to the curriculum, which support development through grades.

Moral Education is often mistaken for general education, whereas Moral Education is a branch of public education with its own peculiarity. Education generally refers to acquiring knowledge, skills, values, and habits (Obaje 2010). It involves formal learning in schools and informal learning through life experiences. Education aims to give individuals the tools they need to succeed academically, professionally, and personally. At the same time, moral Education focuses explicitly on developing ethical and moral values, principles, and behaviours. It aims to cultivate virtues such as

empathy, compassion, honesty, and integrity and to help children understand the difference between right and wrong.

Moral Education is concerned with teaching ethical issues, justice, and the responsibilities of individuals in society. Whereas, education is broad and encompasses various types of learning. Moral Education explicitly emphasizes the development of moral and ethical principles and character. People with formal education might need to learn the practical implementation of the knowledge they have received, but values and morals are a more significant part of society. Ilori (2002) observed that moral education lets the children know what is right and wrong, whereas formal education only states facts and figures.

Importance of Moral Education

The importance of moral education in the foundation of children's character cannot be overemphasized from various walks of life. Moral education plays a vital role in modelling children's character and changes in social and cultural dynamics. One of the essential aspects of moral Education is that it instills moral norms and creates a foundation of ethical values that become a foundation in decision-making (Berkowitz 2012). Children must have a strong moral foundation to face various life situations and challenges amid increasingly complex information flows and interactions. Moral education becomes even more profound when looking at changes in social behaviour and moral crises that occur in forming children's character. Berkowitz points out, "Moral education is not only about teaching the difference between right and wrong but also guiding children to understand and internalize moral values in everyday actions."

Moral Education focuses on building children's character, especially as the world witness evolving social and cultural dynamics shift. Amid global information flows and changing societal values, children are at risk of moral uncertainty that can affect their character development. Moral Education is crucial in providing a solid foundation of ethical values, helping children understand and accept differences, and guiding them in facing complex moral challenges. Furthermore, moral education is essential. It is also interesting to note that education had a religious and moral quality in the past. As a result, not much emphasis was paid to the importance of moral education. Okegbile (2013) listed the following as the importance of moral education:

1. Moral development: Moral education is essential to developing children morally and instilling the desire to be good citizens. They are encouraged to create the proper attitude towards life, their environment, interpersonal relationships, and community.
2. Development of a sound mind: Moral Education prepares children to solve life problems. It encouraged individuals to develop more mature minds in preparation for life's challenges.
3. Learning to Work Independently: An individual must learn to work in groups. At the same time, one must also learn to work alone, and it can be challenging to persuade a child to do that, as one can have solid social needs during that time. Moral education can ensure that children's learn to work independently without being isolated from other students.
4. Learning to Lean towards Practicality: Moral Education is a field that constantly pushes children to practice the skills they learn in the real world. This sends a great message to children, which one can apply to other fields they might pursue in their academic career.
5. Decision-making: Moral Education in the school is meant to help children become autonomous in decision-making and hold up to fundamental values like respect and responsibility. Not only that, but it also meets deep human needs because human lives would be impoverished without it. For a child to grow into a complete person and mature in every respect of human life, he must be fully and genuinely grounded in moral education and experiences. Therefore, it is expedient that the child is allowed to pass through moral education from their early childhood education and place of worship.

Role of Baptist Churches in Moral Education

Generally, the Church's roles in moral education include nurturing, equipping, and providing leading strategies and models that encourage morality. The Church helps to inform, form, and transform a person towards enhancing society's morality (Ayokunle 2016). Considering this, the Baptist Church has a structured Christian education curriculum that teaches children moral behaviour early in life. The Baptist denomination is one of the Evangelical bodies that believe in the final authority of the Bible.

Ayo-Obiremi (2019) further asserted that the Baptist church also encourages moral education by inspiring and motivating children to participate in programs that are organized for them. Such programs as

Sunday school, discipleship lifestyle, Holiday Bible School, Sunday service, Bible club, a day camp, and fun fair facilitate learning ethical and moral behaviour. In light of the preceding, the Baptist denomination observed the following as a means of moral Education to improve moral behaviour in children:

- 1 Baptist Churches emphasize moral Education in the churches and the importance of developing character traits such as humility, patience, self-discipline, and respect for authority. Children are encouraged to cultivate virtues that reflect the teachings of the Bible and emulate the example set by Jesus Christ. Ilori (2005) affirmed that Baptist Churches incorporate moral education into their religious teachings, instilling a sense of moral responsibility and accountability in children, promoting positive behaviour and attitudes toward others.
- 2 Moral Education in Baptist Churches fosters community and encourages children to practice kindness, empathy, and generosity toward others. Children are taught to treat others respectfully, regardless of their background or beliefs. The Church needs to promote the values of love and compassion, and the Church helps children develop moral understanding towards others by fostering a sense of unity and harmony within the Church community through moral education (Ajayi 2010).
- 3 Appropriate Age-graded program: Baptist churches often offer age-graded programs that cater to different stages of development in children and teenagers. These programs are designed to help young people grow in their faith and moral behaviour as they navigate the challenges of adolescence and young adulthood. By providing age-appropriate teachings, activities, and support, these programs can have a significant impact on the moral development of participants. By tailoring their teachings to the specific age group they are working with, Baptist churches can effectively communicate important moral principles in a way that is engaging and relevant to the participants. This can help young people develop a strong moral foundation that will guide their behaviour and decision-making as they grow older.
- 4 Encouraging children's spiritual development: Baptist churches play a vital role in shaping the moral behaviour and spiritual development of children. Through various programs, activities, and teachings, children are given the opportunity to learn about and grow in their faith,

ultimately leading to the development of strong moral values and a deep sense of spirituality. This spiritual foundation provides children with a strong moral framework that helps guide them in making decisions that are in alignment with their faith and values. Children are encouraged to pray, read the Bible, and engage in spiritual practices that help strengthen their relationship with God and deepen their understanding of moral teachings. These activities help children develop a personal relationship with God and deepen their understanding of their faith.

- 5 Also, a chaplain is employed in Baptist-owned schools. Baptist churches enhance moral education by partnering with the education ministry, establishing schools, engaging chaplains to counsel children in the school, facilitating morning devotions and evening programmes, and holding prayer days, amongst other religious practices. The cardinal role of chaplains is the spiritual development of the school community. Ensuring that children are shaped in line with Christian morals, behaviour, and standards (Proverbs 6:22). Nyamai (2008) also opined that among the critical roles of chaplains is helping children go through problems that arise from fears of success or failure in their studies and society's quickly changing attitudes and behaviour.
- 6 Christian professional chaplains are part of schools that embrace the Christian philosophy of education, where God is viewed as the creator of all things and the fountain of all knowledge (Wanza 2012). Chaplaincy services help mould school communities toward desired characters. Wanza outlined the share of good behaviours that should be formed in children. These include consciousness and flourishing life, knowledge and insight, moral virtue and virtuous deeds, friendship and shared warmth, beauty, and aesthetic experience.

Challenges of Improving Moral Behaviour in Baptist Church

The Baptist Church, like many religious institutions, faces numerous challenges when it comes to improving moral behaviour among its members. While the Church is meant to be a place of moral guidance, support, and spiritual growth, it can be challenging to instil and maintain high moral behaviour among its diverse congregation.

- 1 ***Moral Relativism:*** The Baptist Church, like any other institution, operates within the society and is also faced with the challenges in addressing issues of morality which has crept into the church among its

- members. In an increasingly diverse and interconnected world, individuals may come from a wide range of differing beliefs and values. This can make it difficult for the church to establish a set of moral guidelines that are universally accepted and understood by all members.
- 2 ***Cultural diversity:*** One of the main challenges facing the Baptist Church in improving moral behaviour is the diversity of its congregation. The Baptist Church attracts members from more than one cultural background, each having opinions of right or wrong. This diversity makes it difficult, most of the time and in many places, to establish a consistent and unified moral code acceptable to all members. What one person sees as morally good, another may view as ethically wrong.
 - 3 ***Lack of Financial Resources:*** Baptist churches, like all other religious institutions, require funds to carry out various activities and contribute to the development of moral behaviour within the communities. However, the lack of financial resources serves as a significant hindrance to the ability of Baptist churches to effectively fulfil their role in promoting moral behaviour. Without these resources, churches may find it difficult to effectively engage with their communities and provide the guidance and support needed to promote moral behaviour. Moreover, financial constraints limit the ability of Baptist churches to invest in the necessary resources and infrastructure to support their mission. This may include funding for staffing, training, equipment, and facilities.
 - 4 ***Too many activities:*** Many Churches are cumbersome with many activities that occupy time, discouraging the incorporation of a new curriculum that fosters moral education.

Strategies for Harnessing Moral Education As a Tool for Improving Moral Behaviour

1. ***Intentional Curriculum Planning:*** The Church can help improve moral behaviour through an intentionally planned Moral Education curriculum. Irele (2003) asserted that Christian education curriculum should be educational, Spiritual, and moralistic. It is supposed to be Christ-centred and able to impact godly and moral virtues in children. One such children's Sunday school has a place for the whole family. Sunday school can help transform lives and facilitate moral behaviour

within the faith community. Sunday school leaders can also educate children on the need to be law-abiding citizens in the community, and such fellowship builds community; therefore, the children in the Sunday school classes build a stronger Christian community, further extending and strengthening society.

2. ***Mentorship:*** Mentoring is a protected relationship that supports learning and helps individuals develop their potential. A mentoring relationship is one where both mentor and mentee recognize the need for personal development. McMurchy (2014) opined that successful mentoring is based on trust and confidentiality. Therefore, through mentorship, children can improve their moral behaviour. Mentors are more knowledgeable individuals with impeccable moral standing, willing to guide and share experiences with younger ones.
3. ***Moral-Based Bible Study:*** Moral Education can also be incorporated into the Church through Bible study. The entire church family is expected to participate in Bible study, which will be an avenue to spiritual and moral development. (Cite your source)
4. ***Holistic Discipleship Programme:*** Another way to implement moral education in the Church is to encourage a holistic discipleship plan for local church members. One of the discipleship goals is to impact people and teach them the citizens' moral principles, such as integrity, honesty, justice, tolerance, and a sense of duty with discipline. A holistic discipleship programme is not only about spirituality, but an inclusive programme that enhances the discipleship lifestyle through morality. Religious and moral education prepares the child for a meaningful life.
5. ***Annexation of Social Media, Entertainment media, and Christian movies as channels for Moral Education:*** Media and entertainment affect our minds and our being. Media can influence an individual's cognitive, affective, and psychomotor domains. It appeals to the senses of sight and hearing. The media also contributes heavily to forming moral behaviour, positively and negatively (Oloyede 2022). Christians can utilize the media industry to teach children moral Education in contemporary society. The media and entertainment industry includes printed media such as newspapers, magazines, and novels; audio material such as radio broadcasts, the lyrics and music of music; and visual material such as TV programs, videos, films, DVDs, and the internet.

Conclusion

This paper discusses moral education as a tool for improving ethical behavior and the roles of Baptist churches in encouraging children's moral behavior. It is established that Moral Education has contributed to the moral upbringing of the Baptist children and the members, which begins at a tender age. The age-grade curriculum in Baptist denominations, like Sunday school, discipleship, holiday bible school, and worship program outline, has served as a way of helping children develop moral behaviour through the help of the Holy Spirit. It has been further established that through a thorough and effective moral Education in the school and the Church, children can learn moral behavior that will enhance society's progress.

Recommendations

- 1 Local churches should establish clear guidelines and expectations for moral behaviour among children and hold every one of them accountable for their actions irrespective of cultural affiliation.
- 2 Local churches should be willing to harness moral education to improve moral behaviour and be ready to budget and plan for financial obligations.
- 3 Local churches must communicate the importance of improving moral behaviour among children by becoming intentional and emphasizing moral education in their doctrine and curriculum.
- 4 Local churches should champion moral education in contemporary society to educate and guide children in steering moral problems and making ethical decisions.

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